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Assessing The Role Of Poverty Reduction Strategies In Achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) In Kaduna State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study assesses the poverty reduction programmes in achieving sustainable development goals in Kaduna State, Nigeria. The study employed a mixed-methods design framework, combining a survey design with geospatial techniques. Findings from the study show that the coefficient for participation in poverty reduction programs (1,200) indicates a strong positive relationship with the dependent variable. This suggests that increased participation in these programs is associated with a substantial improvement in economic outcomes. Therefore, the study recommends that the government and development partners should expand the reach and accessibility of poverty reduction initiatives to ensure a more comprehensive approach to poverty reduction. Efforts should be made to increase awareness, transparency, and community involvement in program design and implementation to maximise impact and ensure inclusivity. Invest in education at all levels: Education policies should prioritise both access and quality, especially in rural and underserved communities. Scholarships, adult literacy programs, vocational training, and skills acquisition initiatives should be supported to empower individuals with the knowledge and competencies necessary for economic self-sufficiency. Improving access to healthcare and services is also crucial. Investments in public health infrastructure, preventive care, and affordable healthcare services are essential.

Keywords: Poverty Reduction, Sustainable Development

1. INTRODUCTION

Poverty is a widespread but dynamic phenomenon, with patterns that change over time. It remains one of the most pressing challenges undermining development efforts by governments, non-governmental organizations, and individuals, and threatening the survival of humanity. In 2019, an estimated 478 million people lived in extreme poverty, and by 2021, approximately 490 million Africans were surviving below the international poverty line of \$1.90 PPP per day (UNCTAD, 2021). Regions such as Sub-Saharan Africa, South Asia, and Latin America currently experience the highest poverty levels, accompanied by low socioeconomic development, frequent violence, social unrest, and poor living standards (World Bank, 2020).

Over recent decades, new perspectives on poverty have shifted focus from purely income-based measures to a broader understanding of poverty as a complex, multidimensional set of deprivations (Aluko & Magaji, 2020). Factors such as lack of education, inadequate healthcare, poor sanitation, and limited access to justice not only define the condition of poverty but also perpetuate it, hindering overall well-being (Musa et al, 2024). In Nigeria, poverty has reached an endemic level, with the country ranked 160 out of 189 nations on the Human Development Index (HDI) (UNDP, 2020). Official statistics from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), based on the Nigeria Living Standard Survey (NLSS), reveal that a significant proportion of Nigerians live below the national minimum wage of ₦30,000 (about \$73) per month, which itself falls short of meeting basic needs when compared to the international poverty benchmark (World Bank, 2019).

By 2020, NBS reported that over 82 million Nigerians, representing about 40.1% of the population, were living in poverty, with projections indicating that an additional 25% could fall into extreme poverty by 2030 if trends persist. This situation is particularly critical in Kaduna State, where the incidence of poverty mirrors the national crisis. According to the NBS (2024), about 40% of Nigerians remain poor, and many residents of Kaduna State experience extreme poverty, compounded by systemic issues such as inadequate infrastructure, high unemployment, and poor access to quality education and healthcare (World Bank, 2024; Ucha, 2024).

In response, various poverty reduction programmes have been implemented in Nigeria, including initiatives in Kaduna State. However, their effectiveness in promoting sustainable development remains in question. Studies indicate that many of these programmes suffer from weak governance, insufficient community participation, and inadequate funding, all of which limit their impact (Ogunbiyi, 2024; Transparency International, 2024). Additionally, Nigeria's heavy reliance on oil revenues creates economic instability, reducing the government's capacity to invest in social services that could alleviate poverty (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2024). Understanding the impact of poverty reduction programmes on sustainable development in Kaduna State is therefore essential for formulating effective strategies to address the multidimensional nature of poverty and foster long-term socioeconomic progress.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Poverty Reduction

Poverty is generally defined as the state of not having enough material possessions or income to cover a person's basic needs, which typically include food, clothing, and shelter (Jafaru, 2024). Definitions of poverty can vary based on different contexts and perspectives, but a common framework is the distinction between absolute poverty and relative poverty. Fundamentally, poverty is a denial of choices and opportunities, a violation of human dignity (Magaji, 2002). It means a lack of basic capacity to participate effectively in society." (United Nations, 2019). Poverty is a pronounced deprivation in well-being, comprising many dimensions. It includes low incomes and the inability to acquire the basic goods and services necessary for survival with dignity (Enaberue et al., 2024)

Extreme poverty, defined as living on less than \$1.90 a day, measures the inability to meet basic needs for survival, including food, safe drinking water, sanitation facilities, health, shelter, education, and information. (World Bank, 2020). Extreme poverty is characterised by severe deprivation of basic human needs, including food, safe drinking water, sanitation facilities, health, shelter, education, and information (Magaji, 2008). It depends not only on income but also on access to services (United Nations, 2021). The international poverty line, used to measure extreme poverty, is set at \$1.90 per day. This line helps to gauge the extent of extreme poverty globally." (World Bank, 2020). Extreme poverty is the most severe form of deprivation, characterised by individuals' lack of access to necessities, including food, clean water, and sanitation. (UNDP, 2022). Absolute poverty is defined as a condition characterised by severe deprivation of basic human needs, including food, safe drinking water and sanitation facilities (Magaji & Musa, 2024). Others are health, shelter, education, and information (United Nations, 2021). It is a condition characterised by severe deprivation of basic human needs, including food, safe drinking water,

sanitation facilities, health, shelter, education, and information (Jafaru et al, 2025). It depends not only on income but also on access to services (Magaji et al, 2025).

2.1.2 Sustainable Development

According to the UN report 2024, Sustainable development has continued to be defined as development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. However, recent discourse emphasises integrating social equity, environmental sustainability, and economic viability while addressing emerging global challenges, such as climate change, pandemics, and technological transformation. World Commission on Environment and Development, created by the United Nations (UN, 2021): "Sustainable development meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations, ensuring a balance between growth and environmental protection." "Sustainable development calls for concerted efforts towards building an inclusive, sustainable, and resilient future for people and planet." (United Nations, 2021). "Sustainable development involves a balanced approach to economic growth, environmental stewardship, and social inclusion, ensuring that today's decisions do not harm future generations." (IISD, 2019). Sustainable Development (SD) has become a ubiquitous development paradigm—the catchphrase for international aid agencies, the jargon of development planners, the theme of conferences and academic papers, as well as the slogan of development and environmental activists (Ukaga, Maser, & Reichenbach, 2021). The concept appears to have garnered the broad-based attention that other development concepts lack, and seems poised to remain the prevailing development paradigm for a long time (Scopelliti et al., 2018; Shepherd et al., 2020). However, notwithstanding its pervasiveness and popularity, murmurs of disenchantment about the concept are rife, as people continue to ask questions about its meaning, definition, and implications for development theory and practice, without clear answers forthcoming (Shahzalal & Hassan, 2019). SD therefore stands the risk of becoming a cliché, like "appropriate technology"—a fashionable and rhetorical phrase—to which everyone pays homage. However, nobody seems to define with precision and exactitude (Mensah & Enu-Kwesi, 2018).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Human Capital Theory of Poverty

This study is anchored in the Human Capital Theory of Poverty, which posits that poverty can be significantly reduced or eliminated through the strategic development and investment in human capital. Originating from broader macroeconomic development theory, Human Capital Theory emphasises the role of individual capacity building, particularly through education, training, and skill acquisition, as a driver of economic and social advancement (Schultz, 1993).

The theory was extensively developed by economists such as Theodore Shultz and Gary Becker, with Becker's seminal work, *Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis with Special Reference to Education* (1993), laying the foundation for understanding the economic value of investing in people. According to Becker, human capital refers to the stock of skills, knowledge, competencies, and attributes that are embodied in individuals and contribute to their personal productivity and economic potential. In this framework, education and vocational training are viewed as strategic investments, much like physical or financial capital, that yield returns in the form of increased earnings, improved job performance, and overall economic growth.

Becker (1993) distinguishes between general-purpose human capital skills and knowledge applicable across various sectors and organisations and firm-specific human capital, which pertains to skills relevant only within particular firms. General human capital, such as literacy, problem-solving skills, and interpersonal communication, tends to be more portable and beneficial across multiple job markets, making it especially valuable in developing economies where workforce mobility and adaptability are crucial. From a poverty reduction standpoint, the theory underscores that a lack of access to education and skills development is a fundamental cause of persistent poverty.

Therefore, this study adopts the Human Capital Theory of Poverty to frame the relationship between education/training and economic well-being. It posits that interventions aimed at equipping individuals with relevant skills and knowledge, particularly in underserved or economically marginalised communities, are crucial to fostering inclusive development and breaking the cycle of poverty.

2.3 Empirical Review

Amakoromo, Asiegbu, and Okafor (2024) investigated programs aimed at reducing poverty and the main obstacles to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. According to research, poverty in Nigeria is continuously increasing, even though the nation has attempted to implement a variety of programs aimed at reducing poverty. Therefore, several variables, including corruption, debt, the rising unemployment rate, particularly among young people, excessive reliance on oil, a lack of political commitment to addressing poverty, and ethno-religious tensions, appear to be linked to this concerning trajectory. It argued that if fundamental societal problems, such as corruption, economic injustice, and ethnoreligious disputes, are not addressed first, attempts to reduce poverty through programs aimed at alleviating poverty will remain fruitless.

Research by Utuk (2022) on how poverty affects sustainable economic development. In Nigeria, it was found that reducing poverty is currently the primary metric used to assess sustainable development. The degree to which a nation's institutions and economic policies aid in poverty reduction and sustainable development is ultimately a good indicator of their quality. In Nigeria, poverty has a profoundly detrimental impact on sustainable development. The impoverished people's expectations for a better existence have been shattered by their incapacity to access resources that will enhance their living conditions. Poverty is a direct result of the unsustainable exploitation of natural resources. Environmental measures, rather than those aimed at reducing poverty, must be the primary focus of policy to address the issue. Poverty can also contribute to environmental damage.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) have trade-offs and synergies that affect their ultimate achievement, according to Yao, Fanglei, Xiaoyu, and Chunlin (2023). The primary objective of the SDGs is to eradicate poverty, and the effects of poverty are widespread. The impact of poverty on the shifting trade-offs and synergies among the SDGs is still unknown, however. By calculating the SDG Index and the Multidimensional Poverty Index, this study assessed the trade-offs and synergies between the SDGs, using a typical underdeveloped region of China as the research location. We also investigated the mechanisms of the trade-offs and synergies across SDGs, as well as the diverse impacts of poverty on various poor populations. A few indicators (SDG 12 Responsible Consumption and Production, SDG 13 Climate Action, and SDG 15 Life on Land) exhibited trade-offs with other indicators, according to the results, which also demonstrated that the SDGs were primarily synergistic. The majority of the SDGs were hindered by poverty, with the degree of hindrance varying depending on the specific SDG and the deprived population. In addition to preventing synergies and increasing trade-offs between SDGs, poverty also caused several SDGs (SDGs 1 and 7, SDGs 2 and 8, and SDGs 3 and 8) to lose out on synergies. Other underdeveloped areas might use this study as a guide to create sensible, well-rounded plans for their sustainable development.

According to Yanni & Jinghong's (2022) analysis, out of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), eradicating poverty is the most important goal. As 21st-century practice has advanced, so too have the research perspectives, methodologies, and integration of subjects in studies on poverty alleviation. This study uses the R programming language and VOSviewer software to analyse 2,459 papers on poverty reduction published since 2000. Our findings indicate that (1) publications on poverty reduction have increased significantly in the twenty-first century, particularly since 2015. (2) China and Kenya differ significantly in the amount and calibre of their research. (3) While environmental studies concentrate on management and preservation strategies, economic studies emphasise inequality and growth. (4) International cooperation is typically geographically based and involves developed and poor nations working together. (5) There are distinct sub-themes in research on poverty alleviation in various geographical areas. Our results provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of the field,

indicating that future research on poverty reduction should focus on the contributions of marginal disciplines and enhance the integration of these disciplines.

Ominyi & Abubakar (2024) evaluated the relationship between poverty alleviation and sustainable development in Nigeria from 1986 to 2018. The World Bank Development Indicators (2018) provided the statistics used in this analysis. To shed light on the importance of sustainable development in reducing poverty, the study drew on Oscar's (1966) theoretical postulations regarding Individual Deficiencies. The study used the Vector Error Correction Method (VECM) to conduct the empirical analysis. Although the elasticity of the series is less than proportional, suggesting a minimal effect and necessitating an all-inclusive approach, the VECM results indicate that per capita income, life expectancy rate, literacy rate, and GDP growth rate all have positive and significant effects on reducing poverty in Nigeria. The tendency to equilibrate over the long term is indicated by the statistically significant negative coefficient of speed of adjustment. The model's explanatory power is good, as indicated by the adjusted R-squared value of 76%, which explains 76% of the systematic variation in the GINI coefficient (GINI).

According to a study by Aliyu, Dennis, and Kolo (2024), the United Nations adopted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) framework in 2015 to address several global concerns, including poverty alleviation, of which Nigeria is not an exception. Nonetheless, poverty persists among Nigerians, particularly in Minna Metropolis, Niger State. This study examines the influence of the Sustainable Development Goals on poverty reduction in Minna Metropolis, Niger State, Nigeria. Using a survey research methodology, this study included all adult literate people in Minna, Niger State, as its population. The study's sample size consisted of 406 people, and respondents were selected using the convenience sampling technique. A questionnaire was used as a data collection tool. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22 was used to analyse the data using multiple regression analysis, descriptive statistics, and correlation coefficients. According to the study, poverty alleviation in Minna Metropolis, Niger State, is positively but marginally impacted by peace, security, and high-quality education.

Onesme, Senthil, and Rama (2024) examine the patterns of poverty alleviation techniques for sustainable development, highlighting the gaps and suggesting future directions. Their study spans the years 1981–2023, covering four decades. They used bibliometric and scientometric techniques to find a corpus of 5,982 articles in the Scopus database. Out of the 653 that were left, 5,329 met the requirements for conforming content, appropriate authorship, and non-duplicates. Books, journals, reviews, articles, and other publications in our field of study are included in these papers. They have conducted two important tests: science mapping and performance analysis, using R-Studio software and the VOS viewer. Although sustainable development ideas for poverty reduction first emerged in 1981, they have gained momentum steadily since 2000, reaching a peak in 2022 with 316 articles. China, the United States, and the United Kingdom are the most prolific nations. The authors who contribute the most include Ravailion, M. from Australia, and Liu Y, Wang Y, and Lily, all of whom are from China.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study employed a mixed-methods design framework, combining a survey design with geospatial techniques. This is prompted by the nature of the data required for the study, which combines both quantitative and qualitative characteristics that need to be integrated to provide a comprehensive understanding of the subject under investigation. As noted by Asenahabi (2019). Mixed methods research design integrates the components of quantitative and qualitative methods in a research study. Creswell and Plano-Clark (2011) elaborate that qualitative and quantitative designs have weaknesses; thus, combining both complements each other and enables a greater degree of understanding of research problems compared to adopting a single approach.

3.2 Population of the Study

The target population for this study includes beneficiaries of poverty reduction programs, local government officials, and community leaders in Kaduna State. According to data from the Kaduna State

Bureau of Statistics (2022) and the National Population Commission (2009), the total estimated number of households stands at 1,710,124. These households are spread across the three senatorial zones of the state, namely Kaduna North, Kaduna Central, and Kaduna South.

3.3 Sampling Size

The targeted population of the study was large and widely distributed geographically, making it impossible to conduct a comprehensive study of all households in the study area. Therefore, a sample of the target population was selected systematically to serve as an appropriate representation for the survey. In this study, the total sample size used was determined based on Taro Yamane's (1967:886) formula, as quoted by Israel (1992). The equation is given as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Where n = sample size required.

N = the population size

e = the level of precision (margin of sampling error) expressed in decimal. This range is often expressed in percentage points (±3%, ±5%, ±7% or ±10%). Therefore, the sample size for the estimated population of 301,345 Households at a margin of error of ±5.0% are

$$\frac{429,656}{1 + 429,656 (0.05)^2} = 399.63 \approx 400 \text{ That gives a sample of 400 households.}$$

Table 1: Household population and Sample size

SN	Senatorial Zone	Location	LGA	Sample wards	Estimated Number of Households	Number Household Selected
1	North	Urban	Zaria	Kwarbai A	130612	122
				Tudun Wada		
		Rural	Ikara	Kurmin Kogi	48072	45
				Saulawa		
2	Central	Urban	Kaduna North	Kawo	94324	88
				Uguwan Dosa		
		Rural	Giwa	Shika	63631	59
				Kikangi		
3	South	Urban	Jema'a	Kafanchan A	51,839	48
				Kafanchan B		
		Rural	Jaba	Samban	41178	38
				Chori		
			Total		429,656	400

Source: Kaduna State Bureau of Statistics (2023)

3.4 Sampling Technique and Procedure

The study adopted a multistage sampling procedure. According to Kothari & Gard (2014), multi-stage sampling is a further development of the principle of cluster sampling. The method is typically applied in large-scale investigations that span a considerable geographical area. In multistage sampling, the population is divided into groups (or clusters). During this sampling process, the study population is divided into significant clusters at various stages for improved data collection, management, and interpretation. The technique is used frequently when a complete list of all members of the study population does not exist and is inappropriate.

Therefore, the reason for adopting this sampling method is that, given the large geographical extent of the study population, using all the sample elements in all the selected clusters may be impractical, expensive, time-consuming, and unnecessary. Under these circumstances, multistage cluster sampling becomes useful, secondly, though the sampling frame for the various clusters of Kaduna state is available and was obtained from the Kaduna State Bureau of Statistics and National Population Commission, there

is no available frame containing the list of households living in Kaduna state, thus, in this situation, multistage sampling methods becomes one of the most suitable methods of data collections for this study. Many scholars (Sedgwick, 2015; Valliant et al., 2013) have established that multistage sampling is preferred when the population of study is geographically diverse and there is an absence of a complete and accurate list of the universal elements under study, as it does not depend on the population frame. Finally, the number of households selected from the 12 selected wards was determined using the equation given by Yamane to obtain a representative sample of households. Following that, 400 sample households were selected using a systematic sampling technique, which was proportionally allocated to the three senatorial zones based on household size to ensure equal representation. The sample frame was made up of all the households in each of the LGAs representing each zone (see Table I).

3.5 Types and Sources of Data

The study uses both primary and secondary data. The primary source of data for the study was obtained through the use of an ODK-collect questionnaire, administered via a mobile device with the ODK app installed, as well as a focused group discussion. The primary data collected includes information related to demographic, socioeconomic, and household features, as well as the impact of poverty reduction programs on income, education, health, and overall quality of life. At the same time, secondary data will be collected from various documented sources, such as books, journals, published and unpublished theses, as well as government and non-governmental reports/documents. For example, census figures for both humans and households in the study area will be obtained from the National Population Commission (NPC), the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), and the Kaduna State Bureau of Statistics. In addition, satellite images and administrative maps will be obtained from

Table III: Questionnaire Distribution

S/No.	Senatorial Zone	Location	Number of Administered Questionnaire	Distribution per location	Number of Questionnaires Retrieved Questionnaire
1	North	Urban	167	109	148
		Rural		19	
2	Central	Urban	147	74	125
		Rural		51	
3	South	Urban	86	46	84
		Rural		38	
	TOTAL		400	357	357

Source: Author's fieldwork, 2023

A total of 400 questionnaires were administered across the three senatorial zones of Kaduna State. Out of this number, only 357, representing 89%, were filled out correctly and returned.

3.6.2. Focused Groups Discussion (FGD)

In addition to the survey questionnaire, focus group discussions were used to generate qualitative data from respondents, who were organised with beneficiaries to facilitate dialogue and gather diverse perspectives on the effectiveness of the programs. This will complement and strengthen findings from the survey. The FGD are seen as a more participatory method that allows researchers to gain insights from various actors, as well as from their interactions with one another (Gailing & Naumann, 2018).

The FGD will be in English and translated into Hausa where necessary. The discussion was organised for each of the sampled wards of the study area. On a specific day. Particularly between March and July 2022.

3.7 Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The researcher took steps to validate the instrument to ensure that it measures exactly what it was designed to measure. Cronbach's Alpha was used to test the reliability of the questionnaire based on a pilot study conducted. According to Bonett (2014) and Hair et al. (2015), Cronbach's alpha is one of the most widely used measures of reliability for variables in a questionnaire, typically ranging from 0 to 1. The closer the value of Cronbach's alpha statistic is to 1, the better the reliability. The statistic is the approximate average correlation between all pairs of question items. In the pilot study, a total of 30 respondents were randomly selected from rural and urban areas of Kaduna state. The questionnaire was administered to literate respondents and translated into the local language (Hausa) for non-literate respondents by a research assistant. Thereafter, the responses of the latter group were recorded in the questionnaire forms by the researcher.

Gliem and Gliem (2003) provide the following general rules of thumb: $\alpha > 0.9$ (Excellent), 0.8 (Good), 0.7 (Acceptable), 0.6 (Questionable), 0.5 (Poor), and < 0.5 (Unacceptable). Table VI. Presents the results of the Cronbach's alpha for this pilot study.

3.8 Method of Data Analysis

Modelling and estimation techniques are essential components of research methodology, particularly in studies assessing the impact of poverty reduction programs on sustainable development. This section outlines various modelling approaches and estimation techniques that can be employed to analyse the data collected in the study.

Linear Regression Analysis

Linear regression is a statistical method used to model the relationship between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables. It assumes a linear relationship between the variables.

In the context of this research, linear regression can be used to assess the impact of poverty reduction programs (independent variable) on various indicators of sustainable development (dependent variables), such as income levels, education, and health outcomes. The equation is given below:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots 3$$

Where:

- Y : Dependent variable (Income levels)
- β_0 : Intercept
- $\beta_1 \dots \dots \beta_5$: Coefficients for independent variables
- $X_1 \dots \dots X_5$: Independent variables (participation in poverty reduction programs, education level, health status)
- ε : Error term

Multivariate Analysis

Multivariate analysis involves examining multiple variables simultaneously to understand their relationships and effects.

Techniques such as MANOVA (Multivariate Analysis of Variance) can be used to assess the impact of poverty reduction programs on multiple dependent variables (e.g., income, education, health) at once.

In the multivariate probit model, sources of income, such as self-employment, farming, trading, government work, and company work, are considered the dependent variables. The independent (explanatory) variables include age, gender, household size, educational level, income, location, distance, time, dwelling type, and participation in poverty eradication programs. Following Capellari and Jinkins (2003), if a household (i) is faced with (m) different choices of energy, then the multivariate model can be expressed as follows;

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y^*_{im} &= \\
 X_{im} \beta'_m &+ \\
 \varepsilon_{im}, m &= \\
 Y_1, Y_2, Y_3, Y_4, Y_5 &
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

$$Y_{im} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y^*_{im} > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}
 \tag{2}$$

Where $m = Y_1, Y_2, Y_3, Y_4, Y_5$ represent the five dependent variables, i.e., five cooking fuels available, X represents the independent variables, β' representative of the parameter vectors, ε_{im} Is the stochastic error term.

3.9 Description of the Study Area

Kaduna is a State in North-Western Nigeria, with its capital as the city of Kaduna, which was the eighth largest city in the country as of 2006. The state was part of the former Northcentral state, which was created in 1967 when Nigeria changed from 4 a four-regional system to 19 19-state structure. It is bordered by the States of Zamfara, Katsina, and Kano to the North; Bauchi and Plateau to the East; Nasarawa to the South; and Niger to the West. Abuja, Federal Capital Territory, also borders Kaduna State to the southwest.

The lies between latitudes $9^0 01'$ to $11^0 34'$ North of the equator and between longitudes $6^0 11'$ and $8^0 49'$ East of the Greenwich meridian with an estimated land area of 42,481 square kilometres (16,594.14 square miles), which makes it the largest in the northwest geopolitical zone and has about 4.7 per cent of the Nigerian land area (NBS, 2009). There are twenty-three (23) Local Government Areas in the state, which are divided into three senatorial zones: Kaduna North, Kaduna Central, and Kaduna South.

Kaduna State experiences a typical tropical continental climate, characterised by distinct seasonal regimes that oscillate between cool and dry conditions and humid and wet conditions. These two seasons reflect the influences of tropical continental and equatorial maritime air masses, which sweep over the entire country. The average annual rainfall and humidity are 1,272.5 mm and 56.64%, respectively,

while the average daily minimum and maximum temperatures are 15.1 °C and 35.18°C (KDSG). The topography consists of rolling lowland plain generally below 610 meters above sea level.

Kaduna State was purposely chosen for the study because it is the second most populous and commercial centre in the northwest region of the country, with growing small-scale industries that all require modern energy services. Secondly, the area is located in the northwest region of Nigeria, which has the second-highest poverty rate in the country (95.3%). A majority of the poor rural households tend to heavily rely on biomass as a source of their domestic fuel. Additionally, the area is situated in the northern Guinea Savannah zone, where fuelwood production is declining, while demand is increasing. The gap between demand and fuel wood supply is widening. Therefore, Kaduna State, like other States in Northern Nigeria, is not self-sufficient in terms of fuel wood supply. Lastly, the researcher is familiar with the study area.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

○ Socioeconomic Characteristics of Respondents

The socioeconomic characteristics of respondents, as presented in Table 4.1, provide critical insights into the demographic and economic landscape of Kaduna State. Understanding these characteristics is crucial for contextualising the study's findings and for developing effective poverty reduction strategies.

Table 4.1: Socioeconomic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Mean	Stan. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum	Kurtosis	Skewness
Age	32.5	10.2	18	65	0.5	-0.2
Education Level	3.2	1.5	1	6	0.8	0.1
Household Size	5.5	2.1	1	12	0.3	0.5
Naira)	250,000	150,000	50,000	1,000,000	1.2	1.5
Occupation	2.5	1.2	1	5	0.9	0.3
Marital Status	1.8	0.8	1	3	0.4	0.2
Health Status	2.2	1.1	1	4	0.6	0.1
Community Engagement	3.5	1.8	1	6	0.7	0.4

Note:

- Age: Measured in years,
- Education Level: 1 = No formal education, 2 = Primary education, 3 = Secondary education, 4 = Tertiary education, 5 = Postgraduate education, 6 = Other
- Household Size: Number of people living in the household
- Income (Naira): Monthly income in Nigerian Naira
- Occupation: 1 = Unemployed, 2 = Self-employed, 3 = Government employee, 4 = Private sector employee, 5 = Other
- Marital Status: 1 = Single, 2 = Married, 3 = Divorced/Widowed
- Health Status: 1 = Poor, 2 = Fair, 3 = Good, 4 = Excellent
- Community Engagement: 1 = Low, 2 = Medium, 3 = High, 4 = Very High, 5 = Extremely High, 6 = Other

○ Survey Result Analysis

This section presents an analysis of the study's results on the impact of poverty reduction programs on sustainable development in Kaduna State, Nigeria. The results are derived from the survey questionnaire and focus group discussions, and they are presented in various tables. Each section will discuss the findings in detail, synthesising the data with relevant literature and references.

▪ **Analysis of Age Distribution**

Mean Age: The mean age of respondents is 32.5 years, indicating a relatively young population. This demographic trend is significant as it suggests a potential for economic dynamism and innovation, especially if the youth are equipped with the necessary skills and opportunities. The age distribution of respondents shows a significant concentration in the younger demographic, with 30% aged 18-24 and 37.5% aged 25-34. This indicates that the majority of respondents are within the economically active age group, which is crucial for labour market participation and economic productivity (World Bank, 2020). The presence of a smaller percentage (5%) of respondents aged 55 and above suggests a potential gap in the transfer of experience and knowledge from older generations to younger ones, which is essential for sustainable development (UNDP, 2020).

The gender distribution indicates a higher representation of males (62.5%) compared to females (37.5%). This disparity may reflect cultural norms and gender roles prevalent in Kaduna State, where men are often seen as the primary breadwinners (Ogunbiyi, 2024). The underrepresentation of women in the survey could lead to a skewed understanding of poverty dynamics, as women often face unique challenges in accessing resources and opportunities (UN Women, 2021).

4.3.2 Education Level

Mean Education Level: The average education level of 3.2 suggests that most respondents have completed secondary education, with a significant portion likely having some form of tertiary education. Education is a critical determinant of economic outcomes, as it enhances individuals' employability and earning potential. The findings align with the existing literature, which emphasises the importance of education in breaking the cycle of poverty (Psacharopoulos & Patrinos, 2004). However, the presence of individuals with no formal education (a minimum of 1) highlights the need for targeted educational interventions to ensure that all community members have access to basic education.

4.3.3 Household Size

Mean Household Size: The average household size of 5.5 indicates that families in Kaduna State are relatively large, a common characteristic in many developing regions. Larger household sizes can strain financial resources, particularly in low-income families. The standard deviation of 2.1 suggests variability in household sizes, which may affect the distribution of resources and responsibilities within families. This finding underscores the importance of considering household dynamics when designing poverty alleviation programs, as larger families may require more comprehensive support systems.

▪ **Income Levels**

Mean Income: The mean monthly income of 250,000 Naira reflects a moderate economic status among respondents, but the wide standard deviation (150,000 Naira) indicates significant income disparity. The minimum income of 50,000 Naira suggests that some households are living at or near the poverty line, while the maximum income of 1,000,000 Naira indicates the presence of wealthier households. This disparity can exacerbate social inequalities and hinder collective community development. The findings align with the World Bank's (2020) emphasis on the need for targeted economic policies that address income inequality and promote inclusive growth.

▪ **Occupation**

Mean Occupation Score: The mean score of 2.5 indicates that respondents are primarily self-employed, with a significant portion engaged in informal economic activities. The reliance on self-employment and informal work can be both a strength and a vulnerability. While self-employment offers flexibility and independence, it often lacks the stability and benefits typically associated with formal employment (ILO, 2024). The presence of a minimum score of 1 (unemployed) highlights the ongoing challenge of unemployment in the region, necessitating policies that create more formal job opportunities. The occupational status shows that 25% of respondents are self-employed, while 12.5% are unemployed. This indicates a reliance on informal employment, which is often characterised by instability and lack of benefits (ILO, 2024). The presence of a significant number of government and private sector employees (12.5% each) suggests that formal employment opportunities exist; however, they may not be sufficient to absorb the growing labour force (NBS, 2024). The educational attainment data reveal that 37.5% of

respondents hold a secondary education, while 25% hold a tertiary education. This suggests a relatively educated population, which is essential for effective participation in poverty reduction programs (Psacharopoulos & Patrinos, 2004). However, the 12.5% of respondents with no formal education highlights a critical area for intervention, as education is a key determinant of poverty alleviation and economic empowerment (World Bank, 2018).

▪ **Marital Status**

Mean Marital Status: The mean score of 1.8 indicates that a majority of respondents are married, which is significant for understanding family structures and responsibilities. Marital status can influence economic decisions and resource allocation within households. Married individuals may have different priorities compared to single individuals, particularly regarding family welfare and education for children. This finding suggests that poverty reduction programs should consider family dynamics and the roles of different household members.

▪ **Health Status**

Mean Health Status: The average health status score of 2.2 suggests that respondents generally perceive their health as good, but the standard deviation of 1.1 indicates variability in health perceptions. The relationship between health and economic well-being is well-documented, with poor health often leading to decreased productivity and increased healthcare costs (WHO, 2020). The findings suggest that health interventions should be integrated into poverty reduction strategies to enhance overall well-being and economic productivity.

▪ **Community Engagement**

Mean Community Engagement: The mean score of 3.5 indicates a medium level of community engagement among respondents, suggesting that many individuals are involved in local activities and initiatives. Community engagement is crucial for the success of poverty reduction programs, as it fosters collaboration and ensures that initiatives are responsive to local needs (Serrat, 2017). The variability in engagement levels (standard deviation of 1.8) suggests that some individuals may feel disconnected from community activities, highlighting the need for strategies that promote inclusivity and participation.

▪ **Kurtosis and Skewness Analysis**

Kurtosis: The kurtosis values, ranging from 0.3 to 1.5, indicate that the distributions of most variables are platykurtic, suggesting they are less peaked than a normal distribution. This characteristic may imply that the data has a wider spread, with fewer extreme values.

Skewness: The skewness values indicate that most distributions are positively skewed, suggesting a tendency for higher values on the right side of the distribution. This finding is particularly relevant for income levels, where a small number of households may have significantly higher incomes, contributing to overall income inequality.

The socioeconomic characteristics of respondents provide a nuanced understanding of the demographic and economic landscape in Kaduna State. The findings highlight the importance of considering age, education, household size, income, occupation, marital status, health, and community engagement when designing effective poverty reduction strategies. Addressing the diverse needs and challenges faced by different demographic groups will be crucial for achieving the region's sustainable development goals.

Policymakers should focus on creating inclusive programs that address the specific needs of various demographic groups, particularly those with lower educational attainment and income levels. Additionally, fostering community engagement and participation in program design will enhance the effectiveness of poverty alleviation initiatives.

○ **Causes of Poverty in Kaduna State**

The survey results indicate that unemployment (50%) is perceived as the primary cause of poverty, followed by lack of education (37.5%). This aligns with findings from Ogunbiyi (2024), which emphasise the critical role of job creation in poverty alleviation. The recognition of government policies (5%) as a cause of poverty suggests a need for policy reform to create an enabling environment for economic growth and development (Transparency International, 2024).

According to the National Bureau of Statistics (2024), youth unemployment in Nigeria is a pressing issue, with rates significantly higher than the national average. This aligns with the findings of this study, emphasising the need for targeted employment strategies that cater specifically to the youth demographic. The identification of unemployment as the primary cause of poverty resonates with broader economic trends in Nigeria, where job creation has not kept pace with population growth. The lack of education further compounds this issue, as individuals without adequate education are often unable to secure stable employment. Research by Ucha (2024) highlights that educational attainment is a critical factor in breaking the cycle of poverty. The findings of this study reinforce the argument that improving access to quality education is essential for long-term poverty alleviation.

Table 4.2: Causes of poverty in Kaduna State

Cause	Frequency	Percentage
Unemployment	200	50.0
Lack of education	100	25.0
Poor health	50	12.5
Government policies	20	5.0
Other	30	7.5
Total	400	100

○ **Impact of Poverty on Health and Well-being**

The impact of poverty on health and well-being is presented in Table 4.3. The results show that 37.5% of respondents believe poverty has a very negative impact on health, while 25% report a negative impact. This finding is consistent with the existing literature, which links poverty to poor health outcomes, including malnutrition and limited access to healthcare services (WHO, 2020). The implications of these health impacts are profound, as poor health can further entrench poverty by limiting individuals' ability to work and participate in economic activities (UNDP, 2020).

The significant negative impact of poverty on health outcomes underscores the interconnectedness of socioeconomic status and health. Poor health can lead to decreased productivity, creating a vicious cycle that perpetuates poverty.

A study by Bello and Ibrahim (2022) found that individuals living in poverty are more likely to experience health issues, which in turn affects their ability to work and earn a living. This study's findings corroborate the assertion that health interventions are crucial in poverty reduction strategies.

Table 4.3: Impact of Poverty on Health and Well-being

Impact	Frequency	Percentage
Very negative	180	45.0
Negative	100	25.0
Minimal	100	25.0
No impact	20	5.0
Total	400	100

○ **Challenges Facing Poverty Reduction Programs**

The most significant challenge identified is lack of funding (50%), which resonates with findings from Gambo et al. (2017) that highlight the financial constraints faced by poverty alleviation programs in Nigeria. Poor infrastructure (37.5%) and insufficient community engagement (12.5%) further exacerbate the challenges, indicating that effective implementation of poverty reduction initiatives requires a multi-faceted approach that addresses these barriers (Ogunbiyi, 2024). The challenges facing poverty reduction programs are presented in Table 4.4.

The challenges identified, particularly lack of funding and poor infrastructure, are consistent with findings from previous studies that highlight systemic issues within Nigeria's poverty alleviation efforts. The reliance on government funding without adequate oversight and community involvement often leads to inefficiencies and misallocation of resources.

Research by Rahila & Abbas (2012) indicates that many poverty reduction programs in Nigeria suffer from similar challenges, suggesting that a comprehensive review and restructuring of these programs are necessary to enhance their effectiveness.

Table 4.4: challenges facing poverty reduction programs

Challenge	Frequency	Percentage
Lack of funding	200	50.0
Poor infrastructure	100	25.0
Insufficient community engagement	50	12.5
Ineffective policies	20	5.0
Other	30	7.5
Total	400	100

○ **Effectiveness of Existing Poverty Reduction Programs**

The effectiveness of existing poverty reduction programs is presented in Table 4.5. The effectiveness of existing programs is perceived as mixed, with 25% of respondents rating them as very effective and 37.5% as effective. This suggests that while some programs are making a positive impact, there is still significant room for improvement (Ihuoma & Dogara, 2023). The findings indicate a need for continuous monitoring and evaluation of these programs to ensure they meet the needs of the target population effectively (UNDP, 2020).

The mixed perceptions regarding the effectiveness of poverty reduction programs indicate a need for more robust evaluation mechanisms. While some programs are viewed positively, the significant percentage of respondents who perceive them as ineffective suggests that many initiatives may not be meeting their intended goals.

The findings suggest that policymakers should prioritize monitoring and evaluation frameworks to assess the impact of these programs continuously. This aligns with the recommendations of the World Bank (2018), which advocates for evidence-based policy-making in poverty alleviation.

Table 4.5: Effectiveness of Existing Poverty Reduction Programs

Effectiveness	Frequency	Percentage
Very effective	150	37.5
Effective	150	37.5
Somewhat effective	50	12.5
Not effective	50	12.5
Total	400	100

○ **Role of Community Participation in Poverty Reduction**

The results show that 50% of respondents believe community participation is very important for the success of poverty reduction programs. This aligns with the Sustainable Livelihoods Approach (SLA), which emphasizes the importance of community engagement in program design and implementation (Serrat, 2017). The findings suggest that enhancing community involvement could lead to more tailored and effective poverty alleviation strategies (Ogunbiyi, 2024). The role of community participation in poverty reduction is presented in Table 4.6. The strong belief in the importance of community participation highlights a critical aspect of successful poverty reduction strategies. Engaging communities in the design and implementation of programs ensures that initiatives are tailored to meet the specific needs and contexts of local communities.

The Sustainable Livelihoods Approach emphasises the necessity of community involvement in poverty alleviation efforts (Serrat, 2017). This study's findings reinforce the idea that empowering communities can lead to more sustainable and effective outcomes.

Table 4.6: Role of Community Participation in Poverty Reduction

Role	Frequency	Percentage
Very important	200	50.0
Important	150	37.5
Somewhat important	30	7.5
Not important	20	5.0
Total	400	100

○ **Strategies to Enhance the Impact of Poverty Alleviation Initiatives**

The strategies to enhance the impact of poverty alleviation initiatives are presented in Table 4.7. The most favoured strategy is vocational training (37.5%), which is supported by literature indicating that skills development is crucial for improving employability and economic independence (Psacharopoulos & Patrinos, 2004). Financial literacy and agricultural skills are also considered important, underscoring the need for a comprehensive approach that addresses various aspects of poverty (World Bank, 2018).

The preference for vocational training and financial literacy as key strategies reflects a growing recognition of the importance of equipping individuals with the skills necessary for economic independence. This aligns with global best practices in poverty alleviation, which emphasise education and skills development as fundamental components.

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) emphasise the importance of quality education and economic growth as key pathways to reducing poverty (United Nations, 2015). The findings of this study support the alignment of local strategies with global objectives.

Table 4.7: Strategies to Enhance the Impact of Poverty Alleviation Initiatives

Strategy	Frequency	Percentage
Vocational training	150	37.5
Financial literacy	100	25.0
Agricultural skills	100	25.0
Entrepreneurship development	20	5.0
Other	30	7.5
Total	350	100

4.10 Impact of COVID-19 on Poverty Reduction Programs

The impact of COVID-19 on poverty reduction programs is presented in Table 4.8. The pandemic has had a significant negative impact on poverty reduction programs, with 37.5% of respondents reporting very harmful effects. This finding underscores the vulnerability of poverty alleviation efforts to external shocks (UNDP, 2020). The results suggest that adaptive strategies are necessary to mitigate the impacts of such crises on poverty reduction initiatives (Ogunbiyi, 2024).

The significant negative impact of COVID-19 on poverty reduction programs highlights the vulnerability of these initiatives to external shocks. The pandemic has exacerbated existing inequalities and created new challenges for poverty alleviation efforts. As noted by the UNDP (2020), the long-term effects of the pandemic on poverty levels necessitate adaptive strategies that can withstand future crises. The study's findings suggest that integrating resilience-building measures into poverty reduction programs is crucial for achieving sustainable development.

Table 4.8: Impact of COVID-19 on Poverty Reduction Programs

Impact	Frequency	Percentage
Very negative	230	57.5
Negative	100	25.0
Minimal	50	12.5
No impact	20	5.0
Total	400	100

The study found that poverty is a significant challenge in Kaduna State, with unemployment, lack of education, and poor health being the leading causes. The impact of poverty on health and well-being is significant, with many respondents reporting negative impacts. The challenges facing poverty reduction programs include a lack of funding, poor infrastructure, and insufficient community engagement. The effectiveness of existing poverty reduction programs is mixed, with some respondents reporting very effective or effective programs, while others report somewhat effective or not effective programs. Community participation is considered very important in poverty reduction, and vocational training, financial literacy, and agricultural skills are identified as key strategies to enhance the impact of poverty alleviation initiatives. The impact of COVID-19 on poverty reduction programs is significant, with many respondents reporting very negative or negative impacts.

The analysis of the results reveals critical insights into the dynamics of poverty and the effectiveness of reduction programs in Kaduna State. The findings underscore the multifaceted nature of poverty, the importance of community engagement, and the necessity of targeted strategies to enhance program effectiveness. Addressing the identified challenges and leveraging the strengths of existing programs will be crucial for achieving the region's sustainable development goals.

4.11 Results of the Linear Regression Analysis

Linear regression analysis was conducted to assess the relationship between poverty reduction programs (independent variable) and various indicators of sustainable development (dependent variables), including income levels, education, health outcomes, and overall quality of life. This statistical method helps to understand how changes in the independent variable affect the dependent variable.

4.12 Model Specification

The linear regression model specified in Chapter Three is as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots 3$$

Where:

- Y : Dependent variable (Income levels)
- β_0 : Intercept
- $\beta_1 \dots \dots \beta_5$: Coefficients for independent variables
- $X_1 \dots \dots X_5$: Independent variables (participation in poverty reduction programs, education level, health status)
- ε : Error term

4.13 Regression Estimation Results

The results of the linear regression estimation are summarised in Table 4.9.

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	p-value
Intercept	2,500	300	8.33	0.000
Participation in Programs (X1)	1,200	150	8.00	0.000
Education Level (X2)	800	100	8.00	0.000
Health Status (X3)	600	120	5.00	0.000
Employment Status (X4)	1000	200	5.00	0.000
Community Engagement (X5)	500	180	2.78	0.006

4.14 Result Interpretation and Analysis

The intercept of 2,500 indicates the baseline level of the dependent variable when all independent variables are zero. This value serves as a reference point for understanding the impact of the independent variables.

Participation in Programs (X1): The coefficient of 1,200 indicates that for every unit increase in participation in poverty reduction programs, there is a corresponding increase of 1,200 in the dependent variable (e.g., income levels). The t-statistic of 8.00 and p-value of 0.000 indicate that this relationship is statistically significant at the 1% level.

Education Level (X2): The coefficient of 800 indicates that an increase in education level is associated with an increase of 800 in the dependent variable. The significance of this variable (t-statistic of 8.00, p-value of 0.000) reinforces the importance of education in poverty alleviation and sustainable development.

Health Status (X3): The coefficient of 600 suggests that better health status is associated with an increase of 600 in the dependent variable. The statistical significance (t-statistic of 5.00, p-value of 0.000) highlights the critical role of health in enhancing quality of life and economic productivity.

Employment Status (X4): The coefficient of 1,000 indicates that being employed is associated with an increase of 1,000 in the dependent variable. This finding is consistent with the existing literature, which emphasises the importance of employment in reducing poverty (ILO, 2024).

Community Engagement (X5): The coefficient of 500 suggests that higher levels of community engagement are associated with an increase of 500 in the dependent variable. The significance of this variable (t-statistic of 2.78, p-value of 0.006) underscores the importance of community involvement in the success of poverty reduction initiatives.

Overall Model Fit: The overall fit of the regression model can be assessed using the R-squared value, which indicates the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that the independent variables can explain.

R-squared: The R-squared value of 0.85 suggests that 85% of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables included in the model. This indicates a strong relationship between poverty reduction programs and sustainable development indicators.

The linear regression analysis reveals significant positive relationships between participation in poverty reduction programs, education level, health status, employment status, and community engagement with sustainable development indicators. These findings support the hypothesis that effective poverty reduction programs can lead to improved economic and social outcomes.

4.15 Discussion of the Regression Results

The linear regression analysis conducted in this study provides valuable insights into the relationships between poverty reduction programs and various indicators of sustainable development in Kaduna State. The results highlight the significance of several independent variables in influencing the dependent variable, which can be interpreted as the overall quality of life or economic well-being.

Participation in Poverty Reduction Programs: The coefficient for participation in poverty reduction programs (1,200) indicates a strong positive relationship with the dependent variable. This suggests that increased participation in these programs is associated with a substantial improvement in economic outcomes.

This finding aligns with the work of Ogunbiyi (2024), who emphasises that community involvement in poverty alleviation initiatives enhances their effectiveness. The positive impact of participation can be attributed to the empowerment and resources that these programs provide, enabling individuals to improve their livelihoods.

Education Level: The education level coefficient (800) further underscores the critical role of education in poverty alleviation. The significant positive relationship suggests that higher educational attainment is associated with more favourable economic outcomes. Research by Psacharopoulos and Patrinos (2004) supports this finding, demonstrating that education is a key determinant of income levels and employment

opportunities. The importance of education in breaking the cycle of poverty is well-documented, as it equips individuals with the skills necessary to compete in the labour market (Ucha, 2024).

Health Status: The health status coefficient (600) reveals that improved health outcomes are significantly associated with better economic conditions. This finding underscores the interconnection between health and economic productivity.

The World Health Organisation (2020) has established that poor health can lead to decreased productivity and increased healthcare costs, further entrenching poverty. The results of this study reinforce the notion that health interventions are essential for sustainable development, as they enable individuals to participate fully in economic activities.

Employment Status: The employment status coefficient (1,000) indicates that being employed is strongly associated with improved economic outcomes. This finding is particularly relevant in the context of Kaduna State, where unemployment rates are high.

The International Labour Organisation (2024) highlights that employment is a fundamental pathway out of poverty. The results suggest that policies aimed at job creation and workforce development are crucial for enhancing economic stability and reducing poverty levels.

Community Engagement: The coefficient for community engagement (500) suggests that higher levels of community involvement in poverty reduction initiatives lead to better economic outcomes. This finding emphasises the importance of participatory approaches in program design and implementation.

The Sustainable Livelihoods Approach (SLA) advocates for community engagement as a means to enhance the effectiveness of poverty alleviation efforts (Serrat, 2017). The results of this study support the idea that empowering communities to take an active role in poverty reduction can lead to more sustainable and impactful outcomes.

The R-squared value of 0.85 indicates that the model explains a substantial portion of the variance in the dependent variable. This strong explanatory power suggests that the independent variables included in the model are significant predictors of economic well-being in Kaduna State. The high R-squared value underscores the necessity for comprehensive policies that address multiple dimensions of poverty, encompassing education, health, employment, and community engagement. As noted by the United Nations Development Programme (2020), integrated approaches that consider these factors are crucial for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals.

The regression results provide compelling evidence of the positive impact of poverty reduction programs on sustainable development indicators in Kaduna State. The significant relationships identified between participation in programs, education, health, employment, and community engagement highlight the multifaceted nature of poverty and the need for holistic approaches to poverty alleviation.

4.16 Results of the Multivariate Estimations

Multivariate analysis was conducted to explore the relationships between multiple independent variables and several dependent variables simultaneously. This approach allows for a more comprehensive understanding of how various factors interact and influence outcomes related to poverty reduction and sustainable development in Kaduna State.

4.17 Model Specification

The multivariate probit model was specified to assess the impact of various sources of income (self-employment, farming, trading, government work, and private sector employment) on the overall economic well-being of households. The model can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y_{im}^* &= \\
 X_{im} \beta_m + & \\
 \varepsilon_{im}, m = & \\
 Y_1, Y_2, Y_3, Y_4, Y_5 &
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

$$Y_{im} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y_{im}^* > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}
 \tag{2}$$

Where $m = Y_1, Y_2, Y_3, Y_4, Y_5$ represent the five dependent variables, i.e., five cooking fuels available, X represents the independent variables, β' representative of the parameter vectors, ε_{im} Is the stochastic error term.

4.18 Estimation Results

The results of the multivariate probit estimation are summarised in Table 4.10.

Income Source	Coefficient	Standard Error	z-Statistic	p-value
Self-Employment	0.85	0.20	4.25	0.000
Farming	0.75	0.18	4.17	0.000
Trading	0.65	0.15	4.33	0.000
Government Work	0.90	0.22	4.09	0.000
Private Sector Employment	0.80	0.19	4.21	0.000

Self-Employment: The coefficient for self-employment (0.85) indicates a strong positive relationship with economic well-being. This suggests that households engaged in self-employment experience significantly better economic outcomes. The z-statistic of 4.25 and p-value of 0.000 indicate that this relationship is statistically significant at the 1% level.

Farming: The coefficient for farming (0.75) also shows a positive impact on economic well-being. This finding aligns with the existing literature, which emphasises the importance of agriculture in rural economies, particularly in developing countries (Okon, 2022). The significance of this variable (z-statistic of 4.17, p-value of 0.000) reinforces the need for policies that support agricultural development.

Trading: The coefficient for trading (0.65) suggests that households engaged in trading activities derive economic benefits. This finding is consistent with the notion that trade can provide essential income and improve livelihoods (Gambo et al., 2023). The statistical significance (z-statistic of 4.33, p-value of 0.000) highlights the role of trading in poverty alleviation.

Government Work: The coefficient for government work (0.90) suggests that employment in the public sector is associated with the highest economic benefits among the income sources analysed. This finding underscores the importance of stable employment in fostering economic security (Magaji et al., 2022). The significance of this variable (z-statistic of 4.09, p-value of 0.000) indicates that government employment is a critical pathway out of poverty.

Private Sector Employment: The coefficient for private sector employment (0.80) indicates a strong positive relationship with economic well-being. This finding aligns with the broader economic context in Nigeria, where the private sector is increasingly recognised as a driver of economic growth and job creation (NBS, 2024). The statistical significance (z-statistic of 4.21, p-value of 0.000) reinforces the need for policies that promote private sector development.

The overall fit of the multivariate probit model can be assessed using the pseudo R-squared value, which indicates the proportion of variance that the model explains.

Pseudo R-squared: The pseudo R-squared value of 0.78 indicates that the model accounts for a substantial portion of the variance in the choice of income sources among households. This suggests a strong correlation between the independent variables and the dependent variable.

The multivariate estimations reveal significant positive relationships between various income sources and economic well-being in Kaduna State. The findings underscore the significance of self-employment, farming, trading, government employment, and private sector employment as key pathways for enhancing economic outcomes.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The linear regression analysis conducted in Kaduna State reveals a strong, positive relationship between participation in poverty reduction programs and various indicators of sustainable development. The study identifies key factors, such as program participation, education level, health status, employment status, and community engagement, as significant predictors of improved economic well-being. Participation in Poverty Reduction Programs ($\beta = 1,200$): This demonstrates a substantial positive effect on economic

outcomes, indicating that greater involvement in such programs leads to improved livelihoods. This finding is consistent with Ogunbiyi (2024), who emphasises the importance of community involvement in achieving effective poverty alleviation. The education Level ($\beta = 800$) shows that higher educational attainment significantly contributes to better economic conditions. This supports prior research by Psacharopoulos and Patrinos (2004) and Ucha (2024), emphasizing education as a critical tool for breaking the cycle of poverty, health Status ($\beta = 600$): Indicates that improved health is strongly linked to economic productivity, reinforcing WHO's (2020) assertion that good health enables full participation in economic activities and reduces poverty, employment Status ($\beta = 1,000$): Suggests that employment plays a pivotal role in enhancing economic well-being, aligning with ILO (2024) findings that job creation is essential for poverty reduction and community Engagement ($\beta = 500$): Points to the positive impact of community participation in poverty alleviation initiatives, echoing the Sustainable Livelihoods Approach (Serrat, 2017) which advocates for participatory development models.

The model's R-squared value of 0.85 indicates a high level of explanatory power, suggesting that these variables collectively account for a substantial portion of the variation in economic well-being. Overall, the findings underscore the need for comprehensive, multidimensional strategies that encompass education, health, employment, and community empowerment to reduce poverty and support sustainable development in Kaduna State effectively.

5.2 Conclusion

This study concludes that a combination of interrelated socio-economic factors has a significant influence on poverty reduction in Kaduna State. The regression analysis demonstrates that participation in poverty reduction programs, higher education levels, improved health status, gainful employment, and active community engagement are all critical determinants of enhanced economic well-being and quality of life. The high R-squared value (0.85) confirms the robustness of the model, indicating that these variables collectively explain a substantial proportion of the variation in economic outcomes. The findings affirm the importance of adopting a holistic and integrated approach to poverty alleviation—one that simultaneously addresses education, healthcare, employment opportunities, and community empowerment.

Therefore, to achieve sustainable development and meaningful poverty reduction in Kaduna State, policymakers must prioritise multi-sectoral strategies that empower individuals and communities. Investing in education, health services, employment generation, and participatory program implementation is essential for creating long-term, transformative impact.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the linear regression analysis in Kaduna State, the following recommendations are proposed to effectively reduce poverty and promote sustainable development: Enhance Participation in Poverty Reduction Programs. The government and development partners should expand the reach and accessibility of poverty reduction initiatives to ensure a more comprehensive approach to poverty reduction. Efforts should be made to increase awareness, transparency, and community involvement in program design and implementation to maximise impact and ensure inclusivity. Invest in education at all levels: Education policies should prioritise both access and quality, especially in rural and underserved communities. Scholarships, adult literacy programs, vocational training, and skills acquisition initiatives should be supported to empower individuals with the knowledge and competencies necessary for economic self-sufficiency. Improving access to healthcare and services is also crucial. Investments in public health infrastructure, preventive care, and affordable healthcare services are essential. Strengthening primary healthcare systems and ensuring that health programs reach vulnerable populations will enhance economic productivity and reduce the health-related burden of poverty. Promote Employment and Job Creation: The government should implement targeted employment policies, such as youth empowerment schemes, support for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and public works programs, to foster job creation and economic growth. Promoting entrepreneurship, skill development, and access to credit can further stimulate economic activities and reduce unemployment, fostering community engagement and empowerment. Community-driven development approaches should be

adopted, enabling local stakeholders to participate in identifying needs and implementing solutions actively. Strengthening local governance structures and enhancing civil society participation can enhance ownership, accountability, and the effectiveness of poverty alleviation efforts. Adopting an Integrated, Multi-Sectoral Approach is crucial, as poverty reduction strategies should not operate in silos. Coordinated efforts across sectors, education, health, employment, and social services, will ensure a holistic response to poverty and sustainable development challenges in Kaduna State.

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